

RESEARCH ON METHODS FOR IDENTIFYING FORCE MAJEURE SITUATIONS IN CALCULATING TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESSES AT THE STATION

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ANNOTATION This article proposes a method for identifying and mitigating force majeure situations in the calculation of technological processes at the station. Additionally, it introduces a method for calculating the time required for executing technological processes at the station.

Keywords: station, technological process, force majeure, train formation.

АННОТАЦИЯ Предложено выявить форс-мажорные обстоятельства при расчете технологических процессов на станции и устранить их. Разработан метод расчета времени, затрачиваемого на выполнение технологических процессов на станции.

Ключевые слова: станция, технологический процесс, форс-мажор, составление поезда.

Introduction

Due to various shortcomings in timely delivery of cargo by the “O‘zbekiston temir yo‘llari” Joint Stock Company, customer complaints and claims have been increasing. This article aims to calculate the time spent on operations involving both processed and unprocessed wagons at stations.

We will calculate the time spent on technological processes using the example of the first “Ch” sorting station.

The time taken for receiving trains at the station and securing the rolling stock on the park track is $t_{к.к} = 0.25$ hours. $N_{\text{тап}}$, the number of trains to be dispatched per day, is 15. $t_{\text{тех.тпж}}$ -the time spent on technical and commercial inspection of the

wagons, based on the number of wagons in the composition, is 0.7 hours. $v_{\text{кп}}, v_{\text{тех.пнж}}$

- is accepted accordingly.

The waiting time for technical and commercial inspection after the trains have been received is determined according(1) to the following expression:

$$t_{\text{т.к.}}^{\text{к}} = \frac{N_{\text{тар}} \cdot t_{\text{тех.пнж}} (v_{\text{кп}}^2 + v_{\text{т.к.}}^2) \cdot t_{\text{тех.пнж}}}{24 \left(2 \left(1 - \frac{N_{\text{тар}} \cdot t_{\text{тех.пнж}}}{24} \right) \right)} \quad (1)$$

$$t_{\text{тех.пнж}}^{\text{к}} = \frac{15 \cdot 0,7}{24} \frac{(0,7^2 + 0,35^2) \cdot 0,7}{2 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{15 \cdot 0,7}{24} \right)} = 0,12 \text{ hours.}$$

After the technical and commercial inspection, the operations of distributing the composition through the sorting hump are carried out. If the time spent on distributing one composition is $t_{\text{тепа}} = 0.5$ hours, the waiting time until distribution of the compositions is determined according to expression (2) as follows:

$$t_{\text{тепа}}^{\text{к}} = \frac{N_{\text{тар}} \cdot t_{\text{тепа}} (v_{\text{тех.пнж}}^2 + v_{\text{тепа}}^2) t_{\text{тепа}}}{24 \left(2 \left(1 - \frac{N_{\text{тар}} \cdot t_{\text{тепа}}}{24} \right) \right)} \quad (2)$$

$$t_{\text{тепа}}^{\text{к}} = \frac{15 \cdot 0,5}{24} \frac{(0,7^2 + 0,5^2) \cdot 0,5}{2 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{15 \cdot 0,5}{24} \right)} = 0,07 \text{ hours.}$$

Let's denote the factors influencing the overall assembly time of the train composition according to the formation of the train composition. K - the number of organized train directions is 9, C - the composition of the train, $m_{\text{тыз}}$ - when the average number of wagons in the train formation is 60 wagons, $n_{\text{кай.пнш}}$ - when the number of wagons to be reprocessed is conditionally 840, $N_{\text{мак}}$ - when the number

of local wagons is 80, then we calculate the total time spent on the formation of our wagons according to expression (3):

$$t_{\text{т\уп}} = \frac{K \cdot C \cdot m_{\text{т\уз}}}{n_{\text{шт}} + N_{\text{мак}}} \quad (3)$$

$$t_{\text{т\уп}} = \frac{9 \cdot 11 \cdot 60}{840 + 80} = 6,45 \text{ soat}$$

Then the finishing operations of assembling the formed composition are carried out. When $t_{\text{т\уз.т\уг}}$ takes 0.8 hours to complete the assembly, we calculate the waiting time for the completion of assembly according to expression (4):

$$t_{\text{т\уз.т\уг}}^k = \frac{\frac{N_{\text{т\уз}} \cdot t_{\text{т\уз.т\уг}}}{24 \cdot M_{\text{ман}}} (v_{\text{т\уз.т\уг}}^2 + v_{\text{т\уп}}^2) t_{\text{т\уз.т\уг}}}{2 \left(1 - \frac{N_{\text{т\уз}} \cdot t_{\text{т\уз.т\уг}}}{24 \cdot M_{\text{ман}}} \right)} \quad (4)$$

$$t_{\text{т\уз.т\уг}} = \frac{\frac{9 \cdot 0,8}{24} (0,5^2 + 0,4^2) 0,8}{2 \left(1 - \frac{9 \cdot 0,8}{24} \right)} = 0,10 \text{ soat}$$

Once the finishing operations of assembling the composition are completed, the composition is transferred to the dispatch park. The transfer of wagons from the sorting park to the dispatch park is determined as follows: We consider an average of 60 wagons per composition, i.e., $t_{\text{указ}} = (7,5 + 0,08 \cdot 60) / 60 = 0,20$ hours.

After the composition is transferred from the sorting park to the dispatch park, the technical and commercial inspection of wagons is carried out. In this case, the time for technical and commercial inspection amounts to 0.66 hours per wagon. Considering the time for technical and commercial inspection of wagons in the transit park and the time for reprocessed wagons, we determine the waiting time according to expression (5):

$$t_{т.к.}^{к'} = \frac{(N_{тр} + N_{туз}) \cdot t'_{тех.пик} (v_{указ}^2 + v_{тех.пик}^2) \cdot t'_{тех.пик}}{24 \left(1 - \frac{(N_{тр} + N_{туз}) \cdot t'_{тех.пик}}{24} \right)}, \text{ daq} \quad (5)$$

$$t_{т.к.}^{к'} = \frac{(3+9) \cdot 0,66}{24} (0,4^2 + 0,45) 0,66 \left(1 - \frac{(3+9)0,66}{24} \right) = 0,20 \text{ soat}$$

The provision of ready compositions to locomotives in the dispatch park is of great importance. The average waiting time for the provision of locomotives for all transit trains until they are dispatched to the mainline is calculated as follows:

$$t_{лок}^к = \frac{(3+9)(0,7^2 + 0,6^2)}{14} \cdot \frac{24}{2 \left(1 - \frac{(3+9)}{14} \right)} = 4,37 \text{ hours.}$$

In this case, $t_{ж\ddot{y}H}$ represents the time it takes to dispatch the train from the station, which is 0.7 hours.

According to the calculations, the average total time spent on reprocessing wagons at the station is 15.12 hours.

Let's calculate the average time spent waiting for locomotives to be provided for trains that do not undergo reprocessing at the station.

We'll designate the time taken for receiving trains at the station and securing the composition for movement as $t_{к.к.} = 0.25$ hours. Additionally, the time required for technical and commercial inspection of wagons is $t_{т.к.} = 0.66$ hours.

$$t_{т.к.}^{к'} = \frac{(3+9) \cdot 0,66}{24} (0,4^2 + 0,45) 0,66 \left(1 - \frac{(3+9)0,66}{24} \right) = 0,10 \text{ hours.}$$

In this case, $t_{ж\ddot{y}H}$ represents the time it takes to dispatch the train from the station, which is 0.6 hours.

The average waiting time for the provision of locomotives for all transit trains

until they are dispatched to the mainline is calculated as follows:

$$t_{\text{лок}}^{\text{к}} = \frac{\frac{(N_{\text{тп}} + N_{\text{ты3}})}{N_{\text{юк}}} (v_{\text{ты3}}^2 + v_{\text{т.к.}}^2)}{2 \left(1 - \frac{(N_{\text{тп}} + N_{\text{ты3}})}{24 N_{\text{юк}}} \right)} \cdot \frac{24}{N_{\text{юк}}} \quad (6)$$

$$t_{\text{лок}}^{\text{к}} = \frac{\frac{(3+9)}{14} (0,7^2 + 0,6^2)}{2 \left(1 - \frac{(3+9)}{14} \right)} \cdot \frac{24}{14} = 4,37 \text{ hours.}$$

Conclusion

According to the calculations, the average total time spent on wagons that do not undergo reprocessing at the station is 5.98 hours. It's possible to calculate these values for other variations of coefficients as well.

In the process of performing calculations according to the proposed method, a participating route was determined based on the train formation schedule for each dispatch. Subsequently, the movement time on the route was determined based on the quality of train movement graphs. Taking into account the various complexities of working with local wagons at stations, an average time range was calculated for the initial and final operations of the dispatch station in determining the delivery deadline. The empirical times for the remaining at technical stations for the technical operations of wagons were determined based on statements about the consistency of times spent on technological operations.

The application of research results enhances the quality of transportation services provided to freight carriers, improves the efficient use of wagons, and increases competitiveness in railway transportation.

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